

Sea Level Trend 1850-2024

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Abstract

This work describes the determination process of the sea level dataset in 1850-2024.

Data for 1880-2024 are based on measurements, and for 1850-1880, on the parabolic trendline.

The original data are according to various baselines and were converted in this work to the uniform "pre-industrial" 1850-1900 baseline.

In 2024 the global sea level was 258 mm above the 1850-1900 baseline.

The average sea level change in 1994-2024 was 3.33 mm/y.

The acceleration of the sea level rise is currently 0.0164 mm/y², (0.0164 mm/year)/year.

The sea level change per 1°C of global warming decreased from 265 mm/°C in 1980 to 197 mm/°C in 2020.

The dataset is available on the website nowagreen.com.

Glossary

Ave	Average
BL	baseline of surface temperature change (GW), pre-industrial = 1850-1900
CF	Conversion Factor across baselines
GW	Global Warming, global surface temperature above the 1850-1900 baseline, land+ocean, °C
SL	sea level above the pre-industrial 1850-1900 baseline, mm
SL/GW	sea level change per 1°C of global warming, the ratio of sea level change (SL) above the 1850-1900 baseline to the global warming (GW) above the same baseline, mm/°C
TL	trendline

Global Warming Baseline

All global warming and climate change results of calculations in this work are above the pre-industrial 1850-1900 baseline, °C.

Data Sources

Data sources for sea level trend

- NOAA [1]
- NASA [2]

Table 1 - Database for sea level trend

	NOAA	NASA
Reference	[1]	[2]
Units	mm	mm
Records	quarterly	14 days
Selected	Jun-Aug	middle of each year
From	1880	1993
To	2024	2024
Years	145	32
Baseline (BL)	1993-2008	1996-2016
BL years	16	21
Decimal places	2	2
Ave in BL	1.94	0.28

Sea Level Change

NOAA sea level dataset [1] is above the 1993-2008 baseline.

Chart 1 - Change in sea level, mm above 1993-2008 baseline [1]

The current work applies the pre-industrial 1850-1900 baseline to all datasets.

However, the sea level dataset starts in 1880, after 1850.

To convert the sea level dataset to the 1850-1900 baseline, data is required for the 1850-1880 period. The missing data may be calculated using the parabolic trendline.

Table 2 - Parabolic trendline of sea level change 1880-2024 above the 1993-2008 baseline

a	0.008564888898
b	-0.047639747200
c	-177.512387360629
Start	1849

Conversion Factor to 1850-1900 Baseline

The conversion factor for the NOAA [1] dataset from the 1993-2008 baseline is +172.33 mm and for the NASA [2] dataset from the 1996-2016 baseline +195.48 mm.

NOAA and NASA Data Converted to 1850-1900 Baseline

Chart 2 - NOAA [1] and NASA [2] data converted to 1850-1900 baseline, mm

Chart 3 - NOAA and NASA sea level combined data above 1850-1900 baseline, mm

Corrected Parabolic Trendline

Conversion of the NOAA and NASA datasets to the uniform 1850-1900 baseline allows correction of the initial estimation of the 1850-1880 data.

Table 3 - Parabolic trendline of sea level change 1880-2024 above the 1850-1900 baseline

a	0.008203454995
b	0.511879017401
c	0.216920586719
Start	1879

This trendline is applied for the correction of 1850-1880 data.

Sea Level Trend Dataset on Website

The sea level dataset is available on site nowagreen.com [4].

Sea Level Average Change

The average sea level change in 1994-2024 was 3.33 mm/y.

Acceleration of the Sea Level Rise

The parabolic trendline of the sea level is:

$$SL = a*y^2 + b*y + c$$

SL sea level above the pre-industrial 1850-1900 baseline, mm
y year
a, b, c trendline coefficients as in Table 3

First-order derivative:

$$\frac{d(SL)}{dy} = 2ay + b$$

Second-order derivative:

$$\frac{d^2(SL)}{dy^2} = 2a$$

The acceleration of the trendline is the second-order derivative of the parabolic trendline.

As calculated from the trendline in Table 3, the acceleration of the sea level rise is 0.0164 mm/y², (0.0164 mm/year)/year.

Sea Level Change per 1°C of Global Warming

Chart 4 - Sea level change per 1°C of Global Warming, actual data, mm/°C

Considering the 1980-2021 parabolic trendline, the SL/GW parameter changed from 265 mm/°C in 1980 to 197 mm/°C in 2020.

Chart 5 - Sea level change per 1°C of Global Warming considering parabolic trendlines 1910-2021, mm/°C

According to the above chart based on SL and GW trendlines, the SL/GW parameter changed from 463 mm/°C in 1923 to 258 mm/°C in 1980 and 198 mm/°C in 2021, showing a small difference from the previous chart based on actual data.

According to both charts, the SL/GW parameter is currently decreasing.

References

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